

Compounds of Transition Metal Tetrafluoroborates with Oxygen and Nitrogen Bases

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Three types of tetrafluoroborate complexes of nitrogen and oxygen bases with Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) have been prepared and characterised on the basis of their infrared, magnetic moments and conductance studies. $MA_2(BF_4)_2$ type complexes are isolated with Cu(II) when A = acetamide, N-butyramide, benzamide, dimethylacetamide, diethylformamide, acetone, 1:4 dioxane and trimethylphosphate while with nickel(II) and cobalt(II) when A = acetone and 1:4 dioxane. Similarly $[MA_3](BF_4)_2$ type are prepared with Cu(II) when A = N, N-dimethylformamide while with Ni(II) when A = all bases except acetone and 1:4 dioxane and with Co(II) when A = trimethylphosphate. Mixed ligand complexes of Cu(II) and Ni(II) with pyridine (py) and dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) were isolated as $[Cu(py)_2(H_2O)_4](BF_4)_2$, $[Cu(py)_2(DMSO)_2](BF_4)_2$ and $[Ni(py)_2(DMSO)_4](BF_4)_2$.

COMPLEXES of transition metal tetrafluoroborates with a variety of nitrogen and oxygen bases have been reported in literature¹⁻¹⁴. The tetrafluoroborate group normally does not interact with the metal ion but in certain cases it has been found to donate weakly in transition metal complexes with nitrogen bases^{4,5,15}. The coordination of the tetrafluoroborate is normally assigned on the basis of infrared spectra of the polyanion which shows the splitting of the ν_3 band and the appearance of ν_1 band^{4,5,15}. The extent of splitting of ν_3 and the intensity of ν_1 may be taken as an approximate measure of the coordination of BF_4 when compared with the covalent fluoroborate group¹⁵.

A number of compounds of copper(II), nickel(II) and cobalt(II) tetrafluoroborates with a variety of oxygen bases and pyridine have been prepared and studied to understand the environments in which it prefers to form bonds with the metal ion.

Materials and Methods

Metal tetrafluoroborates were prepared by adding the corresponding carbonate to a 40% solution of HBF_4 taken in slight excess¹⁶.

Preparation of complexes :

Compounds of metal tetrafluoroborates with amides were prepared by taking a known weight of the metal salt in an excess of ethyl-orthoformate and adding the required amount of the amide as such or in the form of its solution in ethyl alcohol. The mixture was stirred for a few hours and concentrated under vacuum. It was then allowed to stand as such and cooled till crystals appeared, which were separated, washed with ether followed by petroleum ether and dried. Care was taken to avoid moisture.

Compounds with acetone, 1:4 dioxane and trimethylphosphate were prepared similarly except that the ligand was added in excess.

Compounds with mixed ligands :

$Cu(C_5H_5N)_2(H_2O)_4(BF_4)_2$ was prepared by adding the required amount of pyridine dropwise to $Cu(H_2O)_6(BF_4)_2$ taken in ethyl alcohol. In other cases, metal tetrafluoroborate in slight excess of ethyl-orthoformate was treated dropwise with a mixture of pyridine and dimethylsulphoxide in appropriate ratio. The separation, etc., was done as stated above. All solvents, bases used were purified and dried by well known standard methods.

Elemental analysis :

Copper was estimated iodometrically. Nickel was determined complexometrically by titration against EDTA using murexide as indicator. Cobalt was estimated gravimetrically as $Co(C_5H_5N)_2(CNS)_2$.

Physical measurements :

Magnetic susceptibility was measured by Gouy method using $Hg[Co(NCS)_4]$ as standard. Molar conductance was measured on a conductivity bridge type CL01/01. The infrared spectra were recorded in nujol mull and in KBr pellets on Perkin Elmer 337 grating spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

Ionic tetrafluoroborates are characterised by infrared absorptions at about 1100-1030 cm^{-1} (strong broad), 765 cm^{-1} (very weak) and 522 cm^{-1} (medium broad) arising from ν_3 , ν_1 and ν_4 modes of tetrahedral symmetry¹⁷, respectively. Coordination of the polyanion lowers the original geometry of the

free anion BF_4^- , resulting in the splitting of the ν_3 mode to give sharp strong bands between 1100 to 1000 cm^{-1} and the appearance of a medium to strong intensity band due to ν_1 around¹⁸ 765 cm^{-1} .

Bond formation between an amide molecule and the metal ion generally occurs through carbonyl oxygen¹⁹, with the result that $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ is lowered and $\nu\text{C}-\text{N}$ shows a positive shift²⁰. In primary amides, further the NH stretching mode is shifted to higher spectral region on coordination²⁰.

Ketones coordinate through carbonyl oxygen and the perturbations in the CO modes due to stretching, deformation and bending have been used as a criteria to support the same²¹. The infrared of 1 : 4 dioxane is complicated and does not change much on complexation except minor shifts to indicate that the dioxane molecule has the same expected chair form which it possesses in free state²². Just like other phosphoryl compounds, the coordination of trimethylphosphate is shown by the lowering of the stretching mode of $\text{P}=\text{O}$.

$\text{MA}_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$

Copper(II) forms $\text{CuA}_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$ with all the bases (A) except dimethylformamide whereas Ni(II) and

Co(II) give this complex with acetone and 1 : 4 dioxane only. The infrared of the amide complexes show a lowering of the order of 20–40 cm^{-1} in $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ and a shift to higher region in $\nu\text{C}-\text{N}$ by 10–20 cm^{-1} . νNH in primary amides shows a positive shift of 20–60 cm^{-1} on complex formation (Table 2). The fluoroborate group has been found to be coordinated as evidenced by sharp strong absorptions around 1105, 1070 and 1030 cm^{-1} in addition to the appearance of medium intensity band near 765 cm^{-1} in all amide complexes (Table 2).

The infrared spectrum of pure acetone shows important bands at 1718, 527 and 491 cm^{-1} assignable to CO stretching, deformation and bending modes, respectively²¹. In the present investigations the $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ is lowered by about 80–85 cm^{-1} and δCO and γCO show positive shifts of the order of 35–40 cm^{-1} and 7–10 cm^{-1} respectively. The infrared of 1 : 4 dioxane complexes show minor shifts to indicate its weak bonding monodentate nature²².

In the complex $\text{Cu}(\text{Me}_3\text{PO}_4)_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$, the $\nu\text{P}=\text{O}$ has been observed at 1250 cm^{-1} which when compared with the pure ligand (1280 cm^{-1})²³ shows a lowering of about 30 cm^{-1} , indicating the expected coordination through phosphoryl oxygen.

TABLE I

No.	Compound	Colour	μ_{eff} BM	$\Delta_{1000} 25^\circ$ $\text{cm}^2\text{ohm}^{-1}$ mole^{-1}	Analyses % Found (Calcd.)			
					Metal	C	H	N
I	$\text{CuA}_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Light blue	2.20	187.8 ^a	13.50 (13.41)	20.00 20.27	4.10 4.22	12.00 11.82
II	$\text{NiA}_6(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Light green	3.49	189.8 ^a	10.06 (10.00)	23.86 24.54	4.92 5.11	14.15 14.31
III	$\text{Cu}(\text{Bm})_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Light blue	2.00	42.8 ^b	10.65 (10.85)	32.39 32.82	6.01 6.15	9.27 9.56
IV	$\text{Ni}(\text{Bm})_6(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Light green	3.30	51.3 ^b	7.84 (7.78)	37.46 38.16	6.99 7.15	11.50 11.13
V	$\text{CuB}_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Light blue	1.80	184.8 ^a	8.76 (8.00)	45.89 46.56	3.59 3.88	8.00 7.76
VI	$\text{NiB}_6(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Light green	3.44	191.5 ^a	6.20 (6.11)	52.10 52.46	4.26 4.37	8.84 8.74
VII	$\text{Cu}(\text{DMA})_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Light blue	2.20	51.4 ^b	10.95 (10.84)	32.25 32.79	5.99 6.14	9.23 9.56
VIII	$\text{Ni}(\text{DMA})_6(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Light green	3.23	54.2 ^b	7.90 (7.78)	37.92 38.16	7.00 7.15	10.86 11.13
IX	$\text{Cu}(\text{DEF})_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Light blue	2.24	43.7 ^b	10.00 (9.89)	37.28 37.41	6.49 6.86	8.46 8.73
X	$\text{Ni}(\text{DEF})_6(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Light green	3.32	49.6 ^b	6.48 (7.00)	41.36 42.49	7.81 7.87	9.88 10.02
XI	$\text{Cu}(\text{DMF})_6(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Blue	2.20	48.7 ^b	9.26 (9.40)	31.12 31.97	6.10 6.21	12.18 12.42
XII	$\text{Ni}(\text{DMF})_6(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Green	3.48	60.0 ^b	8.83 (8.75)	31.69 32.20	6.20 6.26	12.31 12.52

TABLE 1(Contd)

No.	Compound	Colour	μ_{eff} BM	$\Delta_{1000}^{25^\circ}$ $\text{cm}^2\text{ohm}^{-1}$ mole^{-1}	Analyses % Found (Calcd.)			
					Metal	C	H	N
XIII	$\text{CuA}'_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Blue	1.94	160.8 ^a	13.13 (13.54)	30.12 30.70	5.01 5.11	— (—)
XIV	$\text{NiA}'_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Green	3.44	165.2 ^a	12.12 (12.64)	30.49 31.03	4.99 5.17	— (—)
XV	$\text{CoA}'_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Red	5.01	167.0 ^a	12.80 (12.88)	30.46 31.00	5.02 5.16	— (—)
XVI	$\text{CuD}_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Blue	2.01	155.2 ^a	10.44 (10.78)	31.92 32.59	5.14 5.43	— (—)
XVII	$\text{NiD}_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Green	3.97	160.0 ^a	10.17 (10.05)	32.12 32.87	5.52 5.48	— (—)
XVIII	$\text{CoD}_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Red	5.47	157.0 ^a	10.37 (10.07)	32.52 32.86	5.41 5.48	— (—)
XIX	$\text{Cu}(\text{TMP})_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Light green	2.10	26.6 ^b	6.70 (6.58)	29.20 29.84	6.01 6.21	— (—)
XX	$\text{Ni}(\text{TMP})_6(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Yellow green	3.34	45.7 ^b	5.42 (5.47)	19.84 20.15	4.86 5.03	— (—)
XXI	$\text{Co}(\text{TMP})_6(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Pink	5.12	43.0 ^b	4.51 (5.49)	20.00 20.14	4.90 5.03	— (—)
XXII	$\text{CuPy}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Light green	2.26	64.2 ^b	13.60 (13.59)	24.82 25.69	3.69 3.85	6.10 5.99
XXIII	$\text{CuPy}_2(\text{DMSO})_2(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Blue	2.25	200.1 ^a	11.60 (11.52)	30.21 30.49	3.84 3.99	5.30 5.08
XXIV	$\text{NiPy}_2(\text{DMSO})_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Light green	3.41	50.9 ^b	8.21 (8.36)	30.11 30.77	4.69 4.84	3.85 3.99

where *a* = nitromethane; *b* = nitrobenzene; A = acetamide; Bm = N-butylamide; B = benzamide; DMA = dimethylacetamide; DEF = diethylformamide; DMF = dimethylformamide; A' = acetone; D = 1 : 4-dioxane; Py = pyridine; TMP = trimethylphosphate; DMSO = dimethylsulphoxide.

In all these complexes of acetone, 1 : 4 dioxane and trimethylphosphate, the fluoroborate group is weakly coordinated as revealed by the appropriate bands around 1075, 1030 and 765 cm^{-1} .

Magnetic moments of copper(II) complexes are normal ranging between 1.80–2.24 BM and those of nickel(II) between 3.44–3.97 BM and cobalt(II) between 5.01–5.47 BM (Table 1), thereby, showing octahedral coordination in each case. All the complexes except $\text{Cu}(\text{Mo}_3\text{PO}_4)_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$ behave as univalent electrolytes in nitromethane or nitrobenzene (Table 1) showing that the weakly coordinated fluoroborate groups leave the coordination sphere in the presence of basic solvents (B) to exist as $[\text{MA}_4\text{B}_2]^{2+}(\text{BF}_4)_2^-$. The complex $\text{Cu}(\text{Mo}_3\text{PO}_4)_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$ is octahedral ($\mu_{eff} = 2.20$ BM) but it is very difficult to understand why it behaves as a univalent electrolyte ($\Delta_{1000} = 26.6 \text{ cm}^2\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{mole}^{-1}$ in nitrobenzene)²⁴. May be that the complex dissociates in nitrobenzene.

$\text{MA}_6(\text{BF}_4)_2$

Nickel(II) forms complexes of this type with all the amides and trimethylphosphate (TMP) while

others form $\text{Co}(\text{TMP})_6(\text{BF}_4)_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{DMF})_6(\text{BF}_4)_2$ (where DMF = dimethylformamide) only. All the complexes show infrared bands characteristic of ionic tetrafluoroborate group and coordinated amides (Table 2). Both the nickel and cobalt complexes of TMP show $\nu\text{P} = \text{O}$ at 1248 cm^{-1} thereby showing a lowering of 32 cm^{-1} , suggesting coordination through phosphoryl oxygen. All the compounds possess magnetic moments characteristic of octahedral geometry and behave as univalent electrolytes (Table 1).

Mixed ligand complexes :

The stretching modes of water are lowered by a few hundred cm^{-1} and the bending mode is raised by 15–40 cm^{-1} on its coordination²⁵. The infrared spectrum of the complex $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4(\text{BF}_4)_2$ shows bands at 3285, 3150 and 3110 cm^{-1} due to νOH of H_2O along with a medium intensity band at 1650 cm^{-1} assignable to OH deformation of coordinated water²⁵. Further the rocking mode of water which becomes infrared active only if metal oxygen bond is sufficiently covalent²⁶, has been observed at 850 cm^{-1} . In addition, the complex

TABLE 2

Compd.+	Amide bands				Tetrafluoroborate bands			Ref.
	$\nu_{as}\text{NH}$	$\nu_s\text{NH}$	$\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$	νCN	ν_3	ν_4	ν_1	
A	3350s	3180s	1665s	1405m	—	—	—	
I	3410s	—	1645s	1420m	1105sh, 1070s, 1030s	530m, 518m	765m	
II	3410s	—	1640s	1620m	1070-1030sb	530m, 518m	—	
Bm	3350s	3200s	1661s	1415m	—	—	—	(28)
III	3380s	3250s	1632s	1425m	1105sh, 1070s, 1030s	530m, 518m	765m	
IV	3380s	3260s	1630s	1425m	1080-1030sb	530m, 518m	—	
B	3360s	3190s	1655s	1395m	—	—	—	(29)
V	3370s	3200s	1635s	1415m	1105sh, 1070s, 1030s	530m, 518m	765m	
VI	3365s	3195s	1635s	1415m	1070-1020sb	530m, 518m	765w	
DMA	—	—	1660s	1480m	—	—	—	(30)
VII	—	—	1625s	1420m	1110sh, 1075s, 1030s	530m, 518m	765m	
VIII	—	—	1628s	1420m	1080-1030sb	530m, 518m	—	
DEF	—	—	1670s	1392m	—	—	—	
IX	—	—	1630s	1420m	1110sh, 1075s, 1030s	530m, 518m	768m	
X	—	—	1635s	1415m	1080-1030sb	530m, 518m	—	
DMF	—	—	1670s	1390m	—	—	—	
XI	—	—	1640s	1415m	1110-1028sb	530m, 518m	765w	
XII	—	—	1635s	1420m	1110-1025sb	530m, 518m	—	

+ = refer Table 1 for complete names and compositions.

s = strong, m = medium, w = weak, sb = strong broad, sh = shoulder.

shows bands at 1618, 1590 1530 and 1460 cm^{-1} assigned to C-N and C-C stretching modes of coordinated pyridine²⁷. A broad band at 1085-1035 cm^{-1} corresponds to ionic fluoroborate. The region at 765 cm^{-1} is interfered by bands of coordinated pyridine. The magnetic moment of the complex is 2.26 BM at room temperature confirming the expected octahedral geometry. The molar conductance (Table 1) agrees with values for univalent electrolytes²⁴.

The oxygen coordination of dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) to the metal atom has been characterised by a shift of the $\nu\text{S}=\text{O}$ from 1053 in pure DMSO to 950 cm^{-1} in complex $\text{Cu}(\text{DMSO})_2(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})_2(\text{BF}_4)_2$ and to 940 in $\text{Ni}(\text{DMSO})_4(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})_2(\text{BF}_4)_2$ and the upward shift of C-S vibration from 697 in ligand to 720 in copper and 715 cm^{-1} in nickel compound⁶. The fluoroborate group is ionic in both the cases as evidenced by broad band in the range 1085-1030 cm^{-1} . The magnetic moment of the copper complex is 2.25 BM at room temperature and since fluoroborate group is ionic, the complex is four coordinated. It is univalent in nitromethane (Table 1). The green nickel compound has an octahedral stereochemistry ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 3.41$ BM) and is univalent in nitrobenzene ($\Delta_{1000} = 50.9 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ mole}^{-1}$).

It may be inferred from molecular compositions that copper in most of the cases forms complexes of the type $[\text{CuB}_4(\text{BF}_4)_2]$, whereas, nickel and cobalt provide compounds $[\text{NiB}_6](\text{BF}_4)_2$, where B is a base. The tetrafluoroborate groups in copper complexes are weakly coordinated to give copper a preferred tetragonal arrangement but in solutions of nitrobenzene or nitromethane, they become labile and leave the coordination sphere. In nickel and cobalt

complexes, however, the tetrafluoroborate group rarely finds an opportunity to coordinate (except in acetone and 1 : 4 dioxane) as most of the complexes are symmetrically hexa-coordinated through ligand molecules.

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